

Attitude of stakeholders towards the use of corporal punishment in selected secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis

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Abstract

This paper examined the attitude of stakeholders on the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population comprised all secondary school teachers, parents and secondary school students in Ilorin Metropolis. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 100 teachers and 100 students while convenient sampling technique was used to select 100 parents who are not into teaching profession, who responded to the questionnaire making a total of 300 sample size. Researchers' designed instrument titled 'Attitude of Stakeholders towards Corporal Punishment Questionnaire' was used to elicit data for the study. The questionnaire was validated by three lecturers from the department of Social Sciences Education, University of Ilorin, Ilorin Nigeria. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach Alpha and the reliability value of the questionnaire stood at 0.71. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of percentage and inferential statistics of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and independent t-test to answer the research question and to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed among others that the attitude of stakeholders on the use of corporal punishment was negative. The study concluded that stakeholders have negative attitude towards corporal punishment as a result of its ineffectiveness in inculcating positive behaviour among secondary school students. It was therefore recommended that teachers should use non-physical disciplinary measures as an alternative to beating or inflicting pains on secondary school students in Ilorin Metropolis.

Keywords: Stakeholders, Attitudes, Corporal Punishment. Secondary School

INTRODUCTION

Parents, teachers, and other adults in every human culture educate a child in the appropriate ways of the group or community to which they belong. This is referred to as socialization in psychology. To achieve this, parents and elders in society play a role in teaching and imprinting desired behaviour through positive reinforcement and the use of punishment to dissuade bad behaviour. The primary foundations for a child's socialization processes are his or her parents. The failure of parental duty as a result of single parenting and the relatively high rate of divorce in our society could be addressed by school. Since children or students spend around eight to ten hours in school, teachers and other school stakeholders can play a vital role in ensuring discipline; by this, students developed a wide range of personality traits, which show up in a variety of ways.

Teachers and other stakeholders are tasked with teaching and monitoring student behaviour, as well as ensuring that students participate in a variety of teaching and learning activities. If learners lack discipline, the intended results of teaching and learning may not be attained in a learning context which can result in wrongdoing within the school environment. Omote et al (2015) noted that the high rate of examination malpractices, laziness, and uncontrolled aggression are symptoms of indiscipline ravaging the students' population in Nigeria. Aside from examination malpractice, there are other misconducts such as stealing, fighting, lying, absent from school and coming late to school just to mention a few. All these acts of indiscipline most especially when it's on the high side could lead the teachers to use corporal punishment.

According to Najoli et al. (2019) corporal punishment refers to intentional application of physical pain as a method of behavior change. It includes the use of physical force intended to cause pain, but not injury, for the purpose of correcting or controlling a child's behavior. Punishing means subjecting a penalty for an offense and usually includes inflicting some kind of hurt; a practice of disciplining in which, something unpleasant is present or positive reinforces are removed following a behavior so that it happens less often in future.

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Swan (2013) described corporal punishment as a disciplinary action in which an older person inflicts bodily pain on a younger person.

Corporal punishment was popular practice in Africa for the purpose of discipline, and its use was frequently viewed as a fundamental aspect of education until the late twentieth century. It has long been assumed that corporal punishment had the capacity to reduce children's misbehaviour. In the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries, corporal punishment was described as inflicting deliberate pain on a child in reaction to the child's undesirable behaviour. The intentional imposition of bodily pain or discomfort on a student by an authority as a penalty for inappropriate behaviour is known as corporal punishment (Farrel, 2014).

In a similar manner, the National Association of School Nurses (2010) described corporal punishment as the intentional infliction of physical discomfort in order to alter wrong behaviour. This can include beating, slapping, spanking, punching, and pinching with implements such as sticks, belts, and paddles. The World Health Organization opposes corporal punishment and views it as an abuse. It claims that teachers should not always chastise students by physically assaulting them. Baumrind et al. (2002) argue that a mild or moderate form of physical punishment such as spanking is an effective and non-detrimental means of instilling discipline and obedience into children.

Egwunyenga (2009) opined that effective discipline does not rely upon external application of consequences designed to elicit compliance; that when desire drives activity, discipline comes from within; and that when good judgment is valued over blind obedience, the students develop a self-dedication that allows them to forgo short-term pleasures in the pursuit of loftier goals. Ali et al. (2014) opined that the major assumption of all behaviours whether adaptive or maladaptive, social or antisocial, defiant or non-defiant, praiseworthy or condemnable is learned and can also be unlearned. It can therefore be said that all manners of indiscipline acts that pervade our secondary school's environment today are learned and can be unlearned through the use of various correctional methods which may not necessarily be corporal punishment.

According to Nwosu et al. (2017) people have different views as touching the use of corporal punishment in schools. Most parents and students might not like the use of corporal punishment in schools. Likewise, many schools' stakeholders are of the view that corporal punishment has no place in today's education. The advancement of technology has made it imperative that teachers develop better ingenious ways of correcting student instead of resorting to corporal punishment while others believe that teaching must necessarily include the use of the cane in a world where indiscipline has taken too deep into the moral attitude of the society. However, it will become unacceptable when flogging gets to the extreme. Some teachers cannot control themselves over a little provocation but descend on students and beat them with any kind of stick available and in the process inflicting severe injuries on their body, the scars of which may have to live with forever (Eyong, 2018).

Although, there are different attitude of stakeholders towards the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools. Corporal punishment is not that bad except if it is not administered appropriately. Use of punishment shows societal disapproval of behaviour. For instance, students that steal another student's notebook or fight in the class and got the other students injured must be punished or asked to do a serious labour. In doing this it will serve as a correction for him or her and deterrent for other students that might want to engage in such act in the nearest future. However, as good as corporal punishment might be in correcting and controlling student's misbehaviour and serving as deterrent to others, it is very important to say that corporal punishment can be misused and will make it lose its value. When a particular punishment is often used it will make students to be frightened and find it difficult to learn.

According to Olasehinde-Williams (2002) when punishment is used to vent the anger of the punisher, it is administered out of proportion to the offender. Rather than reduce the frequency of the occurrence of the behaviour therefore, such punishment may lead to hostility or resentment of authority on the part of the student. Also, students who are severely punished become extremely timid, afraid or hateful of the person who punished them and may respond by running away or withdrawing from class activities. Such students may even come to learn that physical force is an acceptable way of settling conflicts especially with junior ones (Olasehinde-Williams, 2002). According to the African Child Policy Forum (ACPF, 2014), corporal punishment has a negative impact on the physical, psychological and emotional harm of students which can cause poor performance, absence from school, fear of teachers and school, dropout from school for fear of getting beaten, declining self-worth or self-esteem.

There is a highly contestable argument whether the use of corporal punishment has a lasting impact on children's developments. Studies showed that teachers, parents and often children themselves suggest that corporal punishment in schools improves academic performance and corrects bad behaviour (Parkes & Heslop, 2011; Rojas, 2011; Nguyen & Tran, 2013; Morrow & Singh, 2014). However, studies reviewed that many children do not feel that corporal punishment helps them learn or behave rather, it scared, confused, sad and may lead to students becoming violent due to the normalisation of violence (Clacherty et al. 2005; Rojas, 2011; Morrow et al. 2014) From the foregoing it can be deduced that there are disagreement on scholars views and findings on the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools. This contrary views and findings could be as a result of the location of the studies which might not be applicable to the location of the present study.

Statement of the problem

Studies by Odhiambo (2017) and Hakielimu (2011) revealed that corporal punishment has been a routine to many students as they are beaten for almost any mistake or behaviour which does not even require the teachers to use corporal punishment. This is in line with what an independent expert on the United Nations Study expressed that hitting or smacking children is a

type of violence and should not be encouraged in secondary schools (Pinheiro, 2006).

The Federal Ministry of Education got concerned with the way pupils are being punished. It notes that some schools have actually gone beyond the set down regulations of administering corporal punishment. It reminded teachers to administer legal corporal punishment that does not exceed the four strokes per child - no matter what the offence is. This however is being neglected with brutal beatings of secondary school students even to the extent of being administered over 30 lashes. Teachers are allowed to effect the corporal punishment as the rules and guidelines of the ministry, but this should be done in the presence of the school principal so as to enhance regulation which is frequently violated (Ali et al. 2014).

In recent times the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools has become rampant to the extent that students and parents of one of the secondary schools protested against the use of corporal punishment. Because some of the students involved were seriously injured. This might be as a result of the nature of their offence but still not justified as there are rules to the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools. It is noteworthy that students many at times involved in misbehaviours of any kind that while learning they need to be flogged or punished to concentrate on their study. This means that students learn under tears, pain and fear which are negative emotions that could weakens the quality of learning of the students.

Aside the fact that corporal punishment can weakens the quality of learning of students, it can also create ill-feeling between teachers and students which can lead to students lack of concentration in the class and serious unrest in the society. It can further create unnecessary fear among students which might lead to students' mass failure and being dropped out of schools. In view of the forgoing this study attempted to find out attitude of stakeholders (parents, teachers and students) towards the use of corporal punishment in some selected secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis, Ilorin, Kwara state, Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the attitude of stakeholders towards the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis, Ilorin, Kwara State. Specifically, the study examined:

1. The attitude of stakeholders (parents, teachers and students) toward the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis.
2. The difference between stakeholders' (parents, teachers and students) attitude towards the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis.
3. The difference between stakeholders' (parents, teachers and students) attitude towards the use of

corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis based on gender.

The following research questions were raised to sharpen the focus of the study,

1. What is the attitude of stakeholders towards corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis?
2. What is the difference among stakeholder attitude towards the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis?
3. What is the difference among stakeholder attitude towards the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis based on gender?

Two research hypotheses were postulated for this study:

HO₁. There is no significant difference among stakeholders' attitude toward the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis.

HO₂. There is no significant difference among stakeholders' attitude toward the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis based on gender.

METHOD

Descriptive survey method was used to carry out this study. The population of the study comprised all secondary school teachers, parents and secondary school students in Ilorin Metropolis. The simple random sampling technique was used to select 100 teachers and 100 students while convenient sampling technique was used to select 100 parents who are not into teaching profession. The total of 300 respondents formed the sample size for this study. Simple random sampling technique was used to select equal number of respondents (teachers and students) from the selected secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis.

The instrument used for data collection in this study was self-constructed questionnaire titled "Attitude of Stakeholders towards the Use of Corporal Punishment Questionnaire" (ASTUCPQ). The first part of the instrument sought for demographic data of the respondents. The second part contained twenty items that elicited data on stakeholders' attitude towards the use of corporal punishment. The respondents were asked to rate the attitude towards corporal punishment on four-point Likert Scale. Questionnaire was validated by three lecturers from the department of Social Sciences Education, University of Ilorin, Ilorin Nigeria. While the final draft of the questionnaire was pilot tested on an equivalent sample of thirty respondents not used in the main study. The Cronbach Alpha measure of internal consistency was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. The instrument yielded reliability coefficient value of 0.71 which implies that the instrument was reliable. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistic of percentage and inferential statistics of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and independent t-test to test the stated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

To answer the research question, responses of the stakeholders about the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis were summed and subjected to percentage analysis. The instrument contained 20 items that measured attitude towards corporal punishment. These items were rated on scale of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1). Since the test contains 20 items, the maximum obtainable score was calculated as $4 \times 20 = 80$ points while the least point was calculated as $1 \times 20 = 20$ points. The highest score was subtracted from the lowest score $80 - 20 = 60$, and $60/2 = 30$. The result (30) was subtracted from highest score 80 to get 50 which was average. Therefore, stakeholders who score from 20 to 50 were considered as having negative attitude towards corporal punishment while those who score 51 to 80 were considered as having positive attitude towards corporal punishment

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What is the attitude of stakeholders towards corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis? The result is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Attitude of Stakeholders Towards Corporal Punishment in Secondary Schools in Ilorin Metropolis

Attitude	Cutoff Range	Frequency	Percentage%
Positive	51-80	91	30.3
Negative	20-50	209	69.7
Total		300	100

Result in Table 1 shows that 69.7% of the sampled stakeholders had negative attitude towards corporal punishment, while 30.3% of the stakeholders had positive attitude towards corporal punishment. This means that attitude of stakeholders towards corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis was negative.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between stakeholders' (parents, teachers and students) attitude towards the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis.

Results in Table 2 show F-value of 1.84 and p-value of 0.07 in which the p-value is greater than 0.05 ($0.07 > 0.05$). Since 0.07 is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This implied that there is no significant difference in stakeholders' (parents, teachers and students) attitude towards the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis.

Table 2: Analysis of Variance on Difference in Stakeholders' Attitude towards the Use of Corporal Punishment in Secondary Schools in Ilorin Metropolis

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F Values	p
Between Groups	191.693	2	95.846	1.84	.07
In-groups	15465.282	297	52.072		
Total	15656.975	299			

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between stakeholders' attitude toward the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis based on gender.

Table 3: Independent t-test on Difference between Stakeholders' Attitude toward the Use of Corporal Punishment in Secondary Schools in Ilorin Metropolis Based on Gender

Gender	f	Mean	SD	df	t	p
Male	133	46.79	6.62	298	.44	0.66
Female	167	47.45	6.61			

Results in Table 3 revealed a calculated t-value of 0.44 and p-value of 0.66, in which the p-value is greater than 0.05 ($0.66 > 0.05$). Since 0.66 is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This means that there is no significant difference in stakeholders' attitude toward the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis based on gender

DISCUSSION

Finding revealed that the Attitude of stakeholders towards corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis was negative. This implies that the majority of the stakeholders have negative attitudes toward the use of corporal punishment which could be as a result of their experiences in the use of corporal punishment when they were young and students also might have observed how some teachers misused corporal punishment in secondary schools. Moreover, it could also be that it is no longer effective in instilling positive behaviour in students rather it makes them to be more stubborn. This finding is in agreement with the study carried out by Lumato, and Mwila (2022) who found that verbal warning, summoning parents, suspension, doing outside activities, and removing privileges were the common alternative punishments employed in schools in maintaining students' discipline.

This result corroborated the earlier findings of Suda (2005), who reported that physical punishment leads to more vandalism, truancy, pupil violence and a higher dropout rate; that children who get spanked are more likely to lie, to be disobedient at school, and to bully others; that schools that practice caning seem to have a higher delinquency rate leading to rebellion and aggressiveness; that students resist caning and

other forms of disciplinary actions alike for correcting them and tend to organize strikes. While the finding of this study contradicted that of Eremu (2004) who established that physical punishment is not a humiliation but it is needed; that physical punishment should be used in schools because it protects and guides children and that it is useful in the sense that physical punishment guides children and leads them to change bad behaviour.

The second finding of the study revealed that there is no significant difference in stakeholders' (parents, teachers and students) attitude towards the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis. This means that stakeholders involved in this study have negative attitude towards the use of corporal punishment irrespective of their status. This result is in agreement with the findings of Mbikyo (2012) who found that the general observation was that the majority of the parents of students in international schools were not in favour of the continuation of physical punishment. The study further reported that the large number of the teachers in international schools did not want physical punishment to continue in schools.

The finding also showed no significant difference in stakeholders' attitude towards the use of corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis based on gender. This implies that gender of the stakeholders involved in this study has no significant impact on the attitudes of stakeholders in the use of corporal punishment in Ilorin Metropolis. Plausible explanation for this could be that the stakeholders are aware of the child right acts which kick against the use of corporal punishment in schools and at homes. It could also be that the stakeholder irrespective of their gender believed that teachers could misuse corporal punishment in schools and thereby lead to rebellion and revolts by the students. This result is in disagreement with the finding of Ekpeyong et al. (2013) who found that there was a significant difference in the use of corporal punishment on disciplinary control between public and private secondary school students. The differences in the result might be as a result of the location of the study and the years when the studies were conducted. While this study considered stakeholder attitude to corporal punishment, Ekpeyong et al. (2013) study looked at the effect of corporal punishment among private and public schools.

Limitations

The study might have a number of limitations. Although this study was confined to the Ilorin Metropolis, with a sample size limited to selected schools and a subset of parents within the area, it acknowledges that involving other senatorial districts may have yielded different outcomes. Furthermore, while the study primarily focused on the attitudes of teachers, parents, and students towards corporal punishment in secondary schools, it recognizes that incorporating additional stakeholders such as principals, vice-principals, and heads of departments could have altered the generalizability of its findings. Despite these noted limitations, the study maintains its validity through the utilization of empirical techniques for data collection and

analysis. Consequently, the results remain robust and applicable, demonstrating their validity, reliability, and potential generalizability within the state where the research was conducted.

Recommendation

Regular professional development sessions, such as workshops and seminars, are essential for educators to develop disciplinary approaches adapted to address various infractions in secondary schools. Emphasis should be placed on developing non-physical methods of discipline as an alternative to corporal punishment. Educators should also be cool-headed in managing students' misbehaviour and apply discipline with empathy. Given the pervasive negative attitudes towards corporal punishment among stakeholders in Ilorin Metropolis, government intervention to regulate its use in secondary education is imperative. Recognising that corporal punishment has negative emotional and academic consequences for students, it is crucial to underscore the need to deny its legitimacy both legally and culturally in the secondary education setting.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was therefore concluded that parents, teachers and students who are the stakeholders have negative attitude towards corporal punishment in secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis as a result of its ineffectiveness in instilling positive behaviour in secondary school students. Stakeholder negative attitudes towards corporal punishment was as a result of their experience whether as parents, teachers and students. It was also concluded that status of stakeholders have no significant difference in their attitudes towards the use of corporal punishment in secondary school in Ilorin Metropolis which mean stakeholders' status does not in any way negate each other's attitude towards corporal punishment. This connote that corporal punishment is rejected by the stakeholders in this study which could be a reflection of other key actors in the field of education. It was further concluded that stakeholders gender have no significant difference on their attitudes towards corporal punishment in Ilorin Metropolis.

Ethical approval: The research includes human participants and the data were collected upon receiving informed consent from the participants.

Consent to participate: The participants were informed the process of research report.

Availability of data: Data are available in the article.

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